

Micelles : A short review[†]

Animesh Kumar Rakshit

Department of Natural Sciences, West Bengal University of Technology, BF 142, Sector 1, Salt Lake City, Kolkata-700 064, India

E-mail : akrakshi@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : Micelles are formed when surfactants are dissolved in water. The micelles are clusters of surfactant molecules with definite shapes and sizes. However the shape and size of the micelle are functions of the nature of the system. It is generally accepted that micelle formation is entropy dominated. There are theories to explain the formation of clusters, their shapes and their sizes. In this short review some of the theories and experimental results are discussed though no attempt has been made for a comprehensive review of the literature.

Keywords : Micelles, size, shape, theory.

Introduction

It is well known that nature provides some versatile compounds without which it would have been difficult for the life to persist. Surfactants are one such group of compounds which are used in various fields of science from electronics to biology. The two very important and fundamental properties of surfactants are (a) adsorption at an interface which gives rise to foaming, wetting, emulsification, detergency etc. and (b) formation of microheterogeneous surfactant aggregates i.e. micelles leading to solubilization, viscosity etc.¹⁻³. The micelles have also been used in the synthesis of nano particles^{4,5}. In almost all uses of surfactants and there are innumerable number of them, both adsorption and micellization are involved. The surfactants are both man made and nature made. The man made surfactants e.g. sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), Triton X-100 (TX-100) are generally termed synthetic surfactant. The neutral ones e.g. phospholipids are the building block of biological membranes. The versatility of surfactants arise because of the presence of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups in the same molecule thereby providing antagonistic properties among the various parts of the surfactant molecule. For example $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{11}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_{23}\text{OH}$ i.e. Brij-35 is a nonionic surfactant. In this molecule $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{11}$ is hydrophobic

part whereas oxyethylene group i.e. $(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_{23}$ is hydrophilic part providing antagonistic behaviour among themselves by two parts of the same molecule in water. The cloud point i.e. the temperature at which the non-ionic surfactants start to precipitate from its aqueous solution arises because of the presence of these groups in the same molecule⁶.

Critical micelle concentration

Surfactants have been classified as (a) anionic, (b) cationic, (c) nonionic, (d) zwitterionic, (e) polymeric, (f) polyelectrolyte, (g) gemini, (h) bola etc. Many text books^{7,8} and various research articles^{9,10} have discussed this classification. The physicochemical properties of surfactants in aqueous solution, when concentration is slowly increased, in general vary continuously with the amount of surfactant which shows a definite discontinuity at a higher concentration. McBain¹¹ suggested formation of surfactant aggregates which he termed micelle, as the reason for the appearance of this discontinuity at a higher concentration. He opined that at lower concentration only the surfactant monomers exist and at higher concentration both the surfactant monomers and the surfactant aggregates i.e. micelles coexist forming an equilibrium. Though the surfactants are surface active molecules, the micelles are not surface active. The concentration of the

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

surfactant at which the slope change occurs has been termed as "Critical Micelle Concentration" (cmc). Experimentally this transition seems to occur over a very narrow concentration region rather than at a specific concentration. One can say that cmc is the surfactant monomer concentration value X (in mole fraction) which is equal to the total amount of surfactant present in the aggregates¹² i.e. $X_1 = \sum nX_n = X_{\text{cmc}}$. n is the aggregation number which is the number of monomers present in the micelle. CMC has also been defined self-consistently as the concentration where the second derivative of any experimentally observed property with respect to concentration m is zero¹³. This was based on the thermodynamically self-consistent definition of micelle formation developed by Hall^{13,14}. Phillips¹⁵ has stated that the cmc can be identified with the minimum of the second derivative of the experimental data at various concentration i.e. $(\delta\kappa^3/\delta m_t^3)m_t = \text{cmc} = 0$, where κ is any variable property and, m_t , is concentration. This corresponds to the maximum change in the gradient of a solution property vs concentration m_t curve². Nagarajan and Ruckenstein¹⁶ have defined cmc as the surfactant concentration at which the size distribution of micelles changes from a monotonically decreasing function to a function that exhibits extrema. Adam¹⁷ and later Hartley¹⁸ suggested that micelles are spherical in shape (Fig. 1). Hartley¹⁸ actually wrote "The symmetrical asterisk form

Shapes of micelles and vesicles

Fig. 1. Various different shapes of surfactant aggregates.

so frequently drawn would imply a high degree of organization and a density of great magnitude in the centre and of less magnitude near the circumference. It has no physical basis and is drawn of no other reason than that the human mind is an organizing instrument and finds unorganized processes uncongenial". However, it should be recognized that spherical shape of the micelle, though is easy to understand, is only a schematic one and depending upon the concentration of the surfactant, the concentration and nature of the additives, micelles have been found to have non spherical shape like cylindrical, lamellar etc.¹⁹. Leermakers and Scheutjens²⁰ used lattice theory of chain molecules and showed that cmc is theoretically

well defined. The discrepancy that arise between theoretical expectation and experimental observation is because of the low concentration of micelles at cmc²⁰. In their theory they assumed a lattice with a given number of lattice sites of constant volume. Segments of chain molecules and solvent molecules are placed on these sites. The layers are numbered in such a way that it spreads from the centre (no. 1) to the bulk solution. In general the volume of the lattice $V(z)$ is given by

$$V(z) = 2A_s z + \pi h z^2 + (4\pi/3)z^3 \quad (1)$$

where z is a given layer with values of 1, 2, 3,....etc. A_s (area) and h (length) are two parameters which control the geometry of the lattice. A_s and h are zero for a spherical lattice and for rods of length h with hemisphere at each end, A_s is zero. By combining their theory with the thermodynamics of small systems¹⁴, it was shown by the authors, that it was possible to calculate the excess free energy of the micelle with a fixed centre of mass and this excess free energy plays a dominating role in the case of micelle formation. They showed that excess free energy is a function of the number of surfactant molecules per micelle (i.e. aggregation number) and the corresponding plot shows a maximum. Thermodynamically stable micelles are formed at this maximum (Fig. 2). They also indicated that the presence of the positive slope in the plot only indicates the existence of metastable micelles. Further the nature of the curve is expected to change at higher aggregation number indicating the change in the shape e.g. to rods or disks as is shown in Fig. 2 by dotted lines.

Fig. 2. Plot of excess free energy-aggregation number. The maxima presents the thermodynamically stable micelle and the corresponding concentration is cmc. The dotted lines represent change in shape (adapted from Ref. 20).

Shape of the micelles

Micelles are generally assumed to be spherical in shape (Fig. 1). However the shape is really a function of the concentration of surfactant. At low surfactant concentration around cmc the micelle shape is spherical but it changes at higher concentration of surfactant. The presence of electrolyte or other additives also change the shape. Debye did show with light scattering technique that cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) changes from small spherical to cylindrical shape as the NaBr concentration increases in solution¹⁹. Hayashi and Ikeda²¹ observed that sodium dodecyl sulfate forms spherical micelles at low NaCl concentrations ($< 0.45 M$). However it forms rod like micelles at high NaCl concentrations where micelle concentration is high. Static light scattering method was used along with electron micrograph to study CTAB solution²². In aqueous solution CTAB micelles consist of 91 monomers and are spherical. However in presence of NaBr ($> 0.06 M$) rod like micelles are formed, besides spherical micelles. The molecular weight of the CTAB micelle in $0.05 M$ NaBr aqueous solution was estimated to be ~ 3.47 million and also flexible²². Electron micrograph of a specimen from $0.5 M$ NaBr solution shows tortuous thread-like images with a uniform diameter of $4.5\text{--}6$ nm, which can be regarded as flexible rod-like micelles where as specimens from aqueous solutions of CTAB showed spheres of $5\text{--}6$ nm²². Mattoon *et al.*²³ have used X-ray diffraction method to establish that aqueous solutions of *K*-myristate and *K*-palmitate have micelles of cylindrical shape at concentrations of 23 weight percent or more. Vetter²⁴ did use density and viscosity measurements on Aerosol MA (sodium dialkyl sulphosuccinate) aqueous solution to determine the shape of the micelle. Recently Mishael and Dubin²⁵ have shown by turbidimetry, dynamic light scattering etc. that a Triton X-100 micelle or a Triton X100-SDS mixed micelle solubilizes toluene and the micelle size increases. The growth in micelle size was interesting in the sense that in $0.1 M$ NaCl solution the mixed micelle is spherical and remains so when it solubilizes 3 mM toluene. However in $0.5 M$ NaCl solution the pure Triton X-100 micelle as well as the mixed micelle are ellipsoidal or rod-like and when they solubilize 3 mM toluene they become highly elongated. It is interesting to note that in both $0.1 M$ and $0.5 M$ NaCl solutions the volume change of the micelles remained same i.e. 50 nm³. The authors observed that in $0.5 M$ NaCl solution more toluene gets solubilized by mixed micelle and the micelle size increases

but this is then followed by unexpected bimodal size distribution. Gonzalez-Perez *et al.*²⁶ have studied alkylpyridinium salts and found a sphere to rod transition. The second cmc of the ionic amphiphiles was found to be a function of the number of carbon atoms in the hydrocarbon molecular chain, n_C as follows $\ln X_{cmc} = A - B n_C$. Ganguly *et al.*²⁷ have used SANS to study sphere to rod transition of triblock copolymer (PEO)₂₀(PPO)₇₀(PEO)₂₀ micelles at room temperature. They observed that addition of 5–10% ethanol introduces sphere to rod transition of the copolymer micelle at high temperature though in presence of NaCl such transition occurs at room temperature. If NaCl is added in presence of ethanol in the system then also there is transition to rod form of the micelle. This can be observed from the Table 1.

Table 1. Length of rod-like micelles as a function of NaCl concentration for the 10% aqueous solution of the copolymer (PEO)₂₀(PPO)₇₀(PEO)₂₀ with 20% ethyl alcohol content (adapted from Ref. 26)

[NaCl] (mol L ⁻¹)	Length (nm)
1	40.8
2	80.4
3	156.8
3.4	262.6

The micelle formation by a surfactant as well as its shape and size are functions of various variables in the system. The most important one is the solvent water. Water is an unique solvent and has been termed as a non "normal" liquid²⁸. It has high surface tension, very high cohesive energy, high dielectric constant as well as high boiling point due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding. Frank and Evans²⁸ wrote "the nature of the deviations found for non-polar solutes in water, together with the large effect of temperature upon them, leads to the idea that the water forms frozen patches or microscopic "icebergs" around such solute molecules, the extent of the "iceberg" increasing with the size of the solute molecule. Such "icebergs" are apparently formed also about the non-polar parts of the molecules of polar substances such as alcohols and amines dissolved in water, in agreement with Butler's²⁹ observation that the increasing insolubility of large non-polar molecules is an entropy effect". Actually the presence of a hydrophobic group – hydrophilic group combined molecule e.g. surfactant affects

the water structure in the following way : Nonpolar part of the solute forms a clathrate-like cage of waters around it. At low temperature there is large entropy loss to get the hydrogen bonded open "iceberg"-like water structure. At high temperature these intermolecular hydrogen bonds break to gain entropy, at the cost of the enthalpy. The aggregation and other properties of surfactants in solution are influenced by the type of solvent and its polarity, pH, temperature, pressure, and presence of different foreign substances. The foreign substances, because of their property, determine the direction of change of critical micelle concentration (cmc) of the surfactants. It is possible that these substances get distributed between the aqueous and the micellar phase and get accumulated in the palisade layer as well as in the micelle hydrophobic core. Such distribution should favour the stability of the system. Electrolytes generally decrease the cmc, whereas nonelectrolytes may increase or decrease the cmc, and some organic substances, when present in greater amounts, even cause disappearance of the micelles³⁰. Sulthana *et al.*³¹ showed that for dilute solutions of polar additives in an aqueous surfactant solution at cmc, the following general form of the classical Setchenow equation was well obeyed :

$$\log (cmc_w/cmc_{w+A}) = K_M.m'$$

where cmc_w and cmc_{w+A} are the cmc values of a surfactant in the absence and in the presence of additives, K_M is a constant, and m' is the molarity of the additive. This is also true for non polar additives as can be seen from Table 2.

Table 2. K_m (L mol⁻¹), for C₁₂E₁₀ nonionic surfactant in the presence of different sugars at various temperatures (adapted from Ref. 29)

Sugar	308 K	313 K	318 K
D-Ribose	-0.64	-0.73	-0.65
D-Glucose	-1.36	1.03	-1.25
Sucrose	-3.04	-2.53	-2.26

The authors suggested that the additives did not penetrate the micelle that is there was no partition of the additive between the micelle and the solvent. Therefore they suggested that cmc is dependent on the effect of these additives on the bulk solvent properties. They assumed that these additives are located at the micelle-solvent interface. The bulk property of the solvent water does change because of the presence of additives in the solvent.

Further it should be obvious that hydrophilic group of surfactants get hydrated by water. The hydrophobic character can be guessed by hydrophil - lipophil balance (HLB) number - an empirical number first suggested by Griffin³² in 1947. This number weighs the relative effects of the head and tail on the properties of a molecule. From the thermodynamic point of view HLB can be defined as a function of μ_o/μ_w , where μ_o and μ_w are the reference chemical potentials of a surfactant in an oil and water respectively. The ratio can be determined from the partition coefficient of surfactant between oil and water³³.

It has been observed that the size and shape of the micelles depend upon (a) head group size, (b) hydrophobic tail and (c) ionic strength of the solution. Quite often micellar size and shape do change due to changes in the solution condition³⁴. The shape and size of the micelles are not persistent (Fig. 3). Menger³⁴ has stated "that micelles are disorganized "brushheaps" of surfactant molecules with rough surfaces and an abundance of hydrocar-

Fig. 3. The possible randomness of hydrocarbon chain at the core of the micelle.

bon-water contact". However there are examples where it has been shown that the structure of the micelles are persistent (Fig. 4). This persistency in size and shape of micelles arise due either to specific interactions or covalent linkages which may be responsible for micelle formation and there is no change in micellar size or shape³⁵. The authors³⁵ synthesized dendro-calixarene (Fig. 4) which self assembles into completely uniform and structurally persistent micelles. This is an example of a micelle on the molecular scale. The T shape that is observed in Fig. 4 helps in a strong and specific back folding, to small and highly curved aggregates, preventing larger assemblies of low curvature. The solvent mediated hydrogen bonding helps in reducing flexibility and introduces rigidity to the system³⁵. There are many methods which are used to characterize a micelle. These are

Fig. 4. Dendro-calixarene : example of a structurally persistent micelle.

transmission electron microscopy (TEM), light scattering, spectroscopy etc. These methods provide information about size, shape of the micelle. Surface tension measurement can be used to characterize a micelle. However these methods are not good in proving a core-shell structure of a micelle. It has been possible to prove so by using small angle neutron scattering (SANS) or small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) methods. These are noninvasive techniques with nano meter resolution. Core-shell size, radius, density profile, shape etc. of the micelle can be obtained by these methods. There are evidences that micelles are porous cluster. Menger *et al.*³⁶ observed solvolysis at rapid rate of insoluble bis(4-nitrophenyl) carbonate and *p*-chlorobenzhydryl chloride. According to them this result was indicative of the fact that micelles are porous clusters, there are water-filled regions where guests bind hydrophobically. They also used ¹³C NMR, gas solubility as well as molecular models in coming to this conclusion.

Structural transformations in cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) aggregated systems were investigated using positron lifetime spectroscopy³⁷. Positron lifetime measurements were carried out in CTAB/water systems. In here, the molecular aggregation was found to set in at 0.7 mM surfactant concentration (cmc). With increasing surfactant concentration, several transformations in the

micellar structure were found to occur. The results agreed with those obtained from small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), small angle neutron scattering (SANS) and other conventional techniques. It has been shown by Alargova *et al.*³⁸ that rod-like micelles of Na-dodecylpolyoxyethylene-2 sulfate show micellar growth in presence of Ca²⁺ ions.

Models of micelle formation

Hall¹⁴ used thermodynamic arguments to obtain a simple expression for Donnan equilibrium between a solution of charged colloids plus electrolyte and electrolyte solution. The theory developed by Hall when used in ionic surfactant solutions successfully explains agreement with experimental values. Interestingly, (a) the presence of counter ion binding and (b) interaction between micelles are more or less neglected in this approach. However, results are similar to those approaches which consider counter ion binding as well as micellar interaction. The thermodynamic behavior of ionic surfactant solutions in terms of micelle aggregation number, composition and concentration of micelles were obtained.

Micelle formation has been explained by stepwise growth model

S : surfactant molecule

In this model, aggregation is a continuous process. Hence it is very difficult to explain the sudden appearance of micelle at the critical micelle concentration (cmc). However, as the degree of association becomes very large, it almost becomes an all or nothing process and the monomer-micelle transition becomes a first order one. Such first order transition is observed in a phase separation process. Such phenomenon is observed in surfactants with long hydrophobic tail and in these cases "Phase Separation Model" can be used. It is interesting to note that in surfactants with short tail such first order transition is not observed and cmc is somewhat ambiguous³³. It is to be mentioned here that the entropy of micellization for some nonionic surfactants has been found to be very high ($\sim 100 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)³⁹. This generally indicates a phase separation⁴⁰. It should be mentioned here that the phase separation model does not mention anything about micelle sizes. However in mass action model micelles are assumed to be monodisperse.

However in the close aggregation model n number of surfactant molecules suddenly form a cluster i.e. micelle. That is it is a highly cooperative phenomenon. n is the aggregation number. Here one can write

$$nS \leftrightarrow S_n; \text{ and micelle equilibrium constant,}$$

$$K = [S_n] / [S]^n \quad (3)$$

In a micellization process probably there exist an intermediate condition between full cooperativity and a complete noncooperativity. According to Tanford⁴¹ cooperativity arises because of hydrophobicity and noncooperativity is because of the interaction between polar head groups and this is responsible for keeping the micelles at finite size. The aggregation number can be both number average (n_n) as well as weight average (n_w). Camesano *et al.*¹² wrote,

$$n_n = n_{cap} + [K(X - X_1)]^{1/2} \text{ and}$$

$$n_w = n_{cap} + 2[K(X - X_1)]^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where K is the sphere to rod transition parameter and should have a value between $\sim 10^7 - 10^{12}$ for being cylindrical micelle. n_{cap} is the number of molecules present in the endcap region of the cylindrical micelles. X and X_1 are the total surfactant concentration and concentration of singly dispersed surfactant respectively, in mole fraction scale.

Multiple equilibrium model : By using thermodynamic principles it is possible to determine cmc as well as size and shape distribution of micelles in a surfactant system. In the case of equilibrium one can write

$$\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4 = \dots = \mu_n \quad (5)$$

where μ is the chemical potential of surfactant in the aggregate and 1, 2, 3, n are number of surfactants in the aggregates. Therefore one can write

$$\mu_1 = \mu_1^0 + k_B T \ln \gamma_1 X_1 = \mu_n$$

$$= \mu_n^0 + (k_B T/n) \ln (\gamma_n X_n/n) \quad (6)$$

Therefore

$$\gamma_n X_n = n(\gamma_1 X_1)^n \exp [-n(\mu_n^0 - \mu_1^0)/k_B T] \quad (7)$$

where X_n is the mole fraction of the surfactants in the micelle.

Further it is difficult to estimate the activity coefficients of the aggregates and hence for a reasonably dilute solutions these are taken to be unity. Hence the eq. (7) can be written

$$X_n = n(X_1)^n \exp [-n(\mu_n^0 - \mu_1^0)/k_B T] \quad (8)$$

It is therefore possible to determine the size distribution from the $(\mu_n^0 - \mu_1^0)$. The theoretical and experimental data compare well with each other (Fig. 5). The preferred geometry of the micelle can be obtained from

Fig. 5. Volume fraction of monomers (○) and clusters (□) versus the total amphiphile concentration from simulation and calculated mean-field theory augmented with the multiple equilibrium model (eq. (8)) (long-dashed lines) (from Ref. 42, with permission from American Chemical Society).

various different μ_1^0 values for different geometries as it is a function of the geometry like spherical, cylindrical etc. The preferred geometry does have the lowest chemical potential. In this case intermicellar interactions are absent though all intermolecular interactions present in an aggregate are included⁴². Multiple equilibrium model is an extension of mass action model but it does account for the polydispersity of micelle size. Mackie *et al.*⁴² have also discussed Single Chain Mean Field Theory (SCMF) assuming a lattice model for surfactants. In this model space is divided into cubic lattice of sites. Here solvent molecules occupy single sites and surfactants occupy chains of connected sites. The details can be obtained in Reference 43. In this theory (a) chain molecules are the basic unit, (b) reference state is the isolated chain in the solvent, (c) the chain connectivities are considered and (d) the chain structure is independent of the geometry of the aggregate. By computing the probability distribution function of chain conformations under the constrain that there is only single occupancy of the lattice it has been possible to obtain relation which provide both cmc and the micellar size distribution. The SCMF theory pre-

dicts the cmc accurately.

Guerin and Szleifer⁴⁴ studied nonionic amphiphiles by using mean field theory in combination with mass action model and computed cmc, micellar size distribution as a function of head and tail lengths as well as the architecture of the molecules. They observed good agreement between theoretical predictions and molecular dynamic simulation results. The cmc was found to be only slightly dependent on head group architecture. Micelles were found to have compact, solvent free hydrophobic core with head groups at the interface regions.

May and Ben-Shaul⁴⁵ have shown "that the interplay between inter-headgroup and interchain free energies plays a crucial role in determining the shapes and packing free energies of the growing micelles". They stated that "linear, rod like micelles" are generally assumed to have a cylindrical body with two hemispherical ends i.e. a "spherocylinder". If the micelles are rigid it is like rod and in the case of flexibility it is called "worm-like". They suggested that if m is the number of amphiphilic molecules forming a spherical micelle, then the internal packing free energy (i.e. standard chemical potential, μ^0) for n number of amphiphiles ($n \geq m$) is given by

$$\mu^0 = (n - m) f^{cyl} + m f^{sph} \quad (9)$$

$$= n f^{cyl} + m (f^{sph} - f^{cyl}) \quad (10)$$

where f^{cyl} and f^{sph} are molecular packing energies of cylindrical and spherical regions of the spherocylinder. The $[m (f^{sph} - f^{cyl})]$ is the excess molecular packing energy of the spherical part vis-a-vis the cylindrical part. Micellar growth takes place only if this quantity is greater than zero. They showed that for cylindrical micelles the final shape and energy of the endcaps get established only when the micellar length is significantly greater than diameter. This theory also explains the appearance of a second cmc. Decylammonium chloride micelles (concentration range 5–29%) show polydispersed small aggregates undergoing Brownian rotations above cmc but below a second cmc. Above the second cmc, the micelles are rod shaped and grows as concentration increases⁴⁶. Mu *et al.*⁴⁷ as well as Kuni *et al.*⁴⁸ have shown that a second cmc is observed at very high concentration of surfactants and some times have been found at a concentration 100 times more than the normal cmc. Cloud point, ²H magnetic relaxation study are some of the methods that have been used to determine the second cmc. The micelles here are very long (may be a few nanometers) and frequently form with increasing surfactant concentration, due

to added salt or some specific counterions. Porte⁴⁹ has termed such large micelles as "giant micelles". These systems contain "worm-like" or "thread-like" structures as well as "spherical" small micelles. These giant micelles are in continuous "break and reform" mode and have some times been termed "living polymer". The giant polymers are important because of their growing application in oil and gas production, in drag reduction, in shampoos, in personal care products, in drug delivery formulations and similar other uses. The theories, experimental details and applications of Giant Micelles have been recently discussed by various authors in a book edited by Zana and Keller⁵⁰.

There has been attempt to predict the shape and size of micelle. These are :

(a) *Packing parameter* : Israelachvili⁵¹ is of the opinion that spherical micelles have too much of curvature in the peripheral regions and also excessive thickness in the central part. He suggested that the packing parameter, P , could be used as criterion to guess the shape of the micelle and $P = v/Al_c$, where v is the volume of the hydrophobic chain which is incompressible, A is the surface area of the head group and l_c is the chain length of the hydrophobic group of the surfactant monomer. Tanford⁴¹ suggested the following relations at 25 °C for estimating v and l_c . These are

$$l_c = (0.154 + 0.1265C_n) \text{ nm} \quad (11)$$

$$v = (0.0274 + 0.0269C_n) \text{ nm}^3 \quad (12)$$

C_n being the number of carbon atoms in the hydrophobic chain. However the surface area, A , is not easy to obtain. Quite often Gibbs adsorption equation is used to compute this quantity⁵². It should be noted though that the value of A obtained from Gibbs adsorption equation is probably not the correct value⁵³. By using bond length and bond angles, it was possible to estimate head group area⁵⁴ of sodium alkyl sulphate, alkyltrimethylammonium bromide and n -alcohols. They have been estimated to be 0.17, 0.54 and 0.08 nm². The head group area of β -glucosides is estimated to be 0.40 nm². Further the aggregate type depends upon the packing parameter as well as surfactant type as are given in Table 3.

(b) *Thermodynamic model* : Maibaum *et al.*⁵⁵ have used a thermodynamic cycle to explain the formation of micelle. Their theory explains reasonably well the variation of cmc with temperature as well as with the hydrophobic chain length of the surfactant particularly for non-ionic surfactants. The thermodynamic cycle consists of (a) free energy change for the formation of a cavity in the

Table 3. Surfactant type dependent aggregate shape and packing parameter P

Surfactant type	P	Aggregate shape
Single chain, large head group	< 0.33	Spherical/ellipsoidal
Single chain, small head group	0.33–0.50	Cylindrical/rod
Double chain, large head groups, bilayer fluid chain	> 0.5	Vesicles, flexible bilayer
Double chain, small head groups, anionic lipids in high salt	~ 1.0	Planar bilayer
Double chain, small head groups, nonionics	> 1.0	Reverse micelles

solvent, ΔG_1 , (b) free energy change for transferring hydrophobic groups inside the cavity, ΔG_2 and (c) free energy change for placing the hydrophilic groups on the micelle surface or micelle-water interface, ΔG_3 . According to them if one considers an equilibrium between surfactant monomer and surfactant spherical micelle with aggregation number n then one can write

$$\rho = \rho_1 + n \rho_n \quad (13)$$

where ρ , ρ_1 and ρ_n are total surfactant, monomer and n -mer concentration. From statistical thermodynamics one can obtain

$$\rho_n a^3 = (\rho_1 a^3)^n \exp(-\Delta G/kT) \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta G (= \Delta G_1 + \Delta G_2 + \Delta G_3)$ is the driving force for the assembly, a is the girth of the surfactant molecule, k is the Boltzmann constant and T is the absolute temperature. With some further simplifying ideas they obtained the following relation

$$\ln \rho_{\text{cmc}} a^3 = 4.9(\gamma_{\text{ow}} a^2/kT)^{2/3} - \Delta\mu/kT \quad (15)$$

where γ_{ow} is taken as surface tension of water at a given temperature, $\Delta\mu$ is approximately the transfer free energy for moving the associated alkane chain from oil into water. The aggregation number, n , was found to be equal to $3.21 \gamma \delta^2/kT$, where δ is the distance between the hydrophilic group and the alkyl group in the surfactant molecule. They have shown that experimental and calculated data tally well for both cmc as well as temperature variation of cmc (Fig. 6).

Yoshii *et al.*⁵⁶ by large scale molecular dynamics calculation evaluated free energy change when one surfactant molecule (sodium dodecyl sulfate) is added to the spherical micelle of aggregation number " n ". The free energy change profile vs n shows a minimum followed by a maximum. The maximum is seen at $n = 57$ near cmc. The experimental aggregation number is 55–75. It, of course, shows concentration independence of size.

Fig. 6. Plot of cmc vs length of hydrophobic tail at room temperature. Crosses are experimental data (from Ref. 55, with permission from American Chemical Society).

Puvvada *et al.*⁵⁷ suggested a molecular thermodynamic approach where molecular modeling of a surfactant micelle in combination with thermodynamic theory is used to compute the properties of a surfactant solution including the cmc and various thermodynamic properties of micellization. In this molecular thermodynamic approach the following factors are considered. These are (a) water-hydrocarbon chain interaction, (b) curvature effects on interfacial tension, (c) conformational effects at the micellar core and (d) steric and electrostatic interactions. Both a and b of above are affected by the hydrophobic moiety whereas c and d are because of the hydrophilic moiety. The detail of the calculation procedure can be obtained from the original paper⁵⁷. It will be sufficient to say here that it was possible to compute (a) cmc, (b) micelle size distribution, etc. In Table 4 a comparison between theoretical and experimental values are shown. Nagarajan *et al.*⁵⁸ have discussed molecular thermodynamic approach in great detail.

Recently an almost similar approach (though different in details) have been used by Blankstein and his group⁵⁹ which they termed as the computer simulation – Molecu-

Table 4. A comparison between theoretical and experimental cmc values (wt%) for several nonionic surfactants (adapted from Ref. 57)

Surfactants	cmc wt% g dl ⁻¹	
	Experimental	Theoretical
C ₁₂ E ₅	1.0	1.3
C ₁₂ E ₆	2.3	2.3
C ₁₂ E ₈	3.2	4.2
C ₁₀ E ₅	3.5	4.9
C ₁₀ E ₆	8.0	8.5

lar Thermodynamic modeling (CS-MT). In here they stated that each surfactant molecule is modeled as made up of head and tail. The surfactant head is fully hydrated whether it is monomeric or micellar form. However, in the micellar state the surfactant tail is only partially dehydrated with the degree of dehydration being a function of the micelle geometry. Depending upon the degree of hydrophobicity one can distinguish the surfactant head or tail and this can be done by considering group contribution approach. Therefore, it is relatively simple to make educated guesses about the hydration of the surfactant molecules in the micellar state. In this model, the fundamental objective is to compute G_{form} , the free energy associated with the transfer of a surfactant monomer from their standard state to a micelle aggregate in its standard state. The G_{form} is considered to be made up of

$$G_{\text{form}} = G_{\text{tr}} + G_{\text{int}} + G_{\text{pack}} + G_{\text{st}} + G_{\text{elec}} + G_{\text{ent}} \quad (16)$$

where G_{tr} is transfer free energy in transferring solute tails from aqueous solution to bulk solution of solute tails,

G_{int} is the free energy associated with interface formation between tails and water,

G_{pack} is free energy change associated with fixing of solute tail at water-micelle core interface,

G_{st} is free energy for transfer of surfactant heads to the surface of the micelle,

G_{elec} is free energy associated with charging and discharging of surfactant heads and the associated counterions and

G_{ent} is entropic free energy.

The G_{form} is a function of the aggregate shape, the aggregate core-minor radius, the aggregate composition, and the degree of counterion binding. It does have an optimum value. G_{form} (optimum) and the cmc, in mole fraction scale, has been found to be⁶⁰ related

$$\text{cmc} \approx \exp(G_{\text{form}}(\text{optimum})/kT) \quad (17)$$

Blankshtein and his group^{59,60} have discussed in detail methods for computing the G_{form} (optimum). In this computation the formation of micelle hydrophobic core was assumed to be fundamental and the hydration state of the tail remain same whether in monomer or in micelle.

Mixed surfactant systems

As mentioned earlier the uses of surfactant is more

often as a mixture rather than in a pure state. The reason for such use is (a) to avoid the high cost of purifying, (b) the synergistic effect observed in performing properties. Most often mixed surfactant systems show synergistic effect in most performing properties. Further, it should be mentioned here that not only the mixed surfactant but also presence of additives have large effects on the surfactant solution properties. The surfactant technologists need to have knowledge about the mixed systems in order to tailor a formulation for a typical application. For example, if a formulation is to be used as a cleaning detergent then one must know that the concentration of surfactant must exceed the cmc. In various mixed surfactant studies it has been observed that some binary mixed systems have lower cmc than either of the pure. It has been shown⁶¹ that in a mixture of dimeric gemini surfactant (16-4-16) and nonionic $C_{12}E_6$, the cmc values of mixtures with $C_{12}E_6$ mole fraction of 1.0, 0.9, 0.5, 0.1 and 0.0 are 71.0, 0.81, 0.33, 0.36 and 2.72 μM respectively. There are various theories to explain the synergism. The most used one is that of Rubingh⁶². He assumed that Regular Solution theory (RST) is applicable to mixed micelle system where specific pairwise interaction is assumed to be responsible maximally in the free energy of formation of micelle. However, for ionic surfactant systems Poisson-Boltzmann mean field theory (PBMFT) has been used successfully in a quantitative manner. In here specific molecular interactions are neglected⁶³. In RST pair wise interaction between surfactant molecules in a mixed micelle is assumed and the interaction is quantified by an interaction parameter β . If β is zero there is no interaction between the surfactants in a mixed micelle. When β is negative it indicates a strongly attractive interaction between the surfactants in the mixed micelle and a positive β indicates incompatibility among the surfactant species and thus represents a measure of antagonistic behaviour of surfactant combination. The interaction parameter β values for above systems are -13.3, -14.3 and -14.9 for 0.9, 0.5 and 0.1 mole fractions of $C_{12}E_6$, respectively. Recently, Bergstrom *et al.*⁶⁴ have suggested a novel model independent synergy parameter where they use experimental cmc data to evaluate the synergistic effects. They obtained cmc of a mixture of sodium dodecyl sulphate and decyl β -glucoside by surface tension measurement in presence of various concentrations of NaCl. The evaluated model independent β value tallied better with that from PBMFT than the one from RST. Patil *et al.* have studied the thermodynamic and other properties of aqueous β -sulfonato

myristic acid methyl ester (MES)-hexaoxyethylene monododecyl ether ($C_{12}E_6$) mixed surfactant system⁶⁵. They observed a synergistic effect and used RST to obtain the interaction parameter β (Table 5). It is clear that the mixed system shows synergy i.e. there is attractive interaction between the surfactant molecules.

Table 5. The cmc and the interaction parameter β of the β -sulfonato myristic acid methyl ester (MES)-hexaoxyethylene monododecyl ether ($C_{12}E_6$) mixed surfactant system at 303 and 313 °K (adopted from Ref. 65)

X_{MES}	(cmc/mM) β	
	303	313
0.0	(0.071)	(0.051)
0.1	(0.065) -4.85	(0.053) -3.68
0.3	(0.093) -2.13	(0.080)
0.5	(0.120) -2.11	(0.079) -3.32
0.7	(0.129) -3.77	(0.115) -3.17
0.9	(0.365) -2.10	(0.322) -1.76
1.0	2.39	2.63

In a mixed system of ionic tetradecyltrimethyl ammonium bromide/nonionic Brij 35 aqueous solution⁶⁶, the surface tension studies produced two break points as a function of $\log C$. The corresponding concentrations differed by about 1000 units. The second break point (Fig. 7) was taken to be second cmc, the point of sphere to rod transition. The authors reported that conductance method was capable of detecting large micellar aggregates resulting from sphere to rod transition better than methods like surface tension at least in this system.

There are innumerable publications dealing with the binary mixed surfactant systems. However, there are not many publications on ternary systems^{63,67} or systems with

Fig. 7. Plot of surface tension vs $\ln C$ (from Ref. 66 with permission from American Chemical Society).

more number of components because of inherent complexity in such systems. However such systems need detailed studies.

Future direction

Formation of micelles in a surfactant solution is now well recognized. Various experimental results indicate that the micelles are generally spherical in shape but changes to other shapes at higher concentration. Further presence of additives like salts, sugars etc. also affects the cmc, aggregation number and shape of the micelles. There have been theoretical attempts to explain and reproduce the experimental observations. In this mini review some of these experimental results and the theoretical attempts have been mentioned though not very comprehensively. The author believes that though the theories do reproduce the experimental results in some cases – it is not a general phenomenon. No one theory explains all observations. Prediction of cmc, aggregation number and shape of micelles still remains a tricky one. However it seems molecular thermodynamic approach is reasonably successful though further research, both theoretical and experimental, are need of the time.

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